

IMPLOSION OF CYLINDRICAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES SUBJECTED TO UNDERWATER IMPULSIVE LOADS

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ABSTRACT

The dynamic response of filament wound laminated cylindrical carbon-fiber/epoxy composite structures subjected to underwater impulsive loads is analyzed. This study focuses on temporal and spatial evolution of deformation and fluid-structure interactions. The effect of structural attributes and material properties on load-carrying capacity, deflection, energy dissipation and damage are of particular interest. The designs studied are monolithic composite structures and sandwich structures with foam cores of different relative densities and varying radii of curvature. The cylindrical structures are subjected to transverse side-on impulsive loads which are generated using a novel experimental setup called the Underwater Shock Loading Simulator (USLS). The experiments are supported by fully dynamic, coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian (CEL) finite-element simulations which account for fluid-structure interactions and damage and failure mechanisms in the different materials. For the same applied impulse, the monolithic cylindrical sections experience significant warping, delamination and cracking, while sandwich structures experience significantly lower damage. As the core density of the sandwich structures increases, the transmitted impulse and overall damage also increase. Deflection and warping in the impulsively-loaded region are influenced by the radius of curvature and material orientation. Filament-wound structures experience lower deflection and higher recovery in comparison to laminated structures. Overall, the cylindrical sandwich structures are found to have superior blast-resistance than the cylindrical monolithic structures of equal mass with only relatively minor increases in wall thickness. The experiments, computations and structure-performance relations offer avenues for improving the blast mitigation capabilities of cylindrical composite sections in critical parts of structures like keel, hull and underwater pipelines

1 INTRODUCTION

Marine structures are designed to operate in hostile environments consisting of corrosive sea water, hot and cold temperature extremes, transient dynamic loads like hull slamming and complex three dimensional hydrodynamic loads. Additionally, naval structures are required to withstand weapons impacts and blast loads resulting from surface and underwater explosions. Recent assessments of marine structures have demonstrated that sandwich composites can provide good blast mitigation due to their high strength to weight ratios and high shear and bending resistances. Characterization of the behavior of composite materials and polymeric foams under impulsive loading is a prerequisite for the analysis and design of effective, blast resistant sandwich composites. Deformation and failure due to dynamic loading in layered materials such as composite laminates has been the subject of numerous investigations in recent years. Gas gun based impact loading has been successfully used to generate impulsive loading through water [1-3]. A major aspect of marine composite structures that has not been thoroughly investigated is the response of cylindrical composite structures to blast loads. The objective of the present work is to characterize the dynamic deformations and damage response of curved sandwich composites with different core densities but similar total masses subjected to high intensity underwater impulsive loads. The analysis focuses on the effect of varying structural attributes and material properties on load-carrying capacity, deflection, energy dissipation and damage.

This is a combined experimental and computational study. Computationally, the cohesive finite element method (CFEM) is employed to track the fracture processes. The major fracture mechanisms include interlaminar delamination between composite plies with different fiber orientations, intralaminar cracking, core cracking and core-face debonding. In the CFEM framework, there are two main approaches to resolve crack initiation and growth. One approach is to insert cohesive elements ahead of the crack tip as the crack grows [4]. This method can avoid the cohesive surface induced stiffness reduction of the overall model caused due to a finite stiffness of the cohesive traction-separation relation. However, this approach is computationally expensive and requires specific fracture initiation criteria. Another approach involves embedding cohesive surfaces along all finite element boundaries as an intrinsic part of the physical model [5, 6]. The constitutive behavior of bulk phases and cohesive surfaces are specified separately. Dynamic crack initiation and growth can be tracked using this framework. Additionally, proper choice of cohesive surface stiffness and finite element size can alleviate and minimize the cohesive surface induced stiffness reduction [7].

2 EXPERIMENTAL FACILITY AND DIAGNOSTICS

Planar underwater impulses are generated using a novel experimental setup called the Underwater Shock Loading Simulator (USLS). The USLS consists of a projectile impact based impulsive loading mechanism and clamped and simply supported boundary conditions. The cylindrical structure is supported on a steel flange because this loading condition closely resembles that found in a naval structure. A force transducer is mounted on the flange to measure impulses transmitted in each case. The location of the failure modes in this configuration allows accurate time resolved measurements using high-speed digital imaging. Specifically, high-speed digital imaging and digital image correlation enables the study of deflection, face wrinkling, core face debonding, core compression, core shear cracking and rupture and their dependence on load intensity and core characteristics. This experimental setup is shown in Figure 1. The USLS can generate impulsive loads with peak pressures within the range 40-250 MPa, which resemble those created by an underwater explosion. Figure 2 shows the pressure histories of underwater impulses corresponding to different projectile velocities.

Figure 1 Sectional view of Underwater Shock Loading Simulator showing the setup for high speed digital imaging and digital image correlation of impulsively loaded cylindrical sandwich structures.

3 MATERIALS

The composite specimens are constructed with glass fiber reinforced plastic with two winding angles [45°] and [-45°]. The wall thickness of monolithic cylindrical specimens is 5.5 mm. For the sandwich structure, the outer face is 3.5 mm thick, the inner face is 2.5 mm thick and the sandwich core is 10 mm thick. The core material is Divinycell HP100 PVC foam manufactured by DIAB Inc. [8]. Figure 3 shows the different components of a filament wound composite cylinder. The sandwich structure is manufactured by cutting the PVC foam into the required segments, inserting into

concentric composite cylinders and impregnating the assembly with polyester resin. The inside surfaces of the cylindrical specimens are painted with an enamel spray to improve reflectivity for high-speed photography.

Figure 2 (a) The pressure profiles of impulsive waves in the water chamber measured in experiments for four different projectile velocities; (b) the corresponding normalized incident impulses (\bar{I}).

Figure 3 Components of filament-wound, cylindrical fiberglass structure with $[45^\circ]/[-45^\circ]$ orientation.

4 NUMERICAL MODEL

4.1 Modeling of water-structure interaction

The model consists of a Lagrangian domain for the solids and an Eulerian domain for the water. In the Lagrangian domain, nodes are fixed within the material and nodal displacements track the material deformation. Since each Lagrangian element is always 100% within a single material, the material boundary coincides with element boundaries. In contrast, Eulerian the domain consists of nodes that are fixed in space and the material flows through the elements that do not experience deformation. Eulerian elements may also be partially or completely void, allowing material to flow into empty space, capturing cavitation, a crucial aspect of fluid flow. Materials tracked by Eulerian elements can interact with Lagrangian elements through Eulerian-Lagrangian contact algorithms to allow fully coupled multi-physics simulations like fluid-structure interactions. This Coupled Eulerian-Lagrangian

(CEL) framework allows the severe deformation in water and the FSI to be captured. In addition to simulating the blast wave propagation in the USLS, the Eulerian formulation also captures the exponentially decaying pressure waves and resulting cavitation at the fluid-structure interface. The interaction between the water and structure is effected by tying the nodes in the water to the corresponding nodes of the structure, thereby ensuring continuity of displacements when contact occurs.

The response of water in the Eulerian domain is described by the Mie-Grüneisen equation of state with a linear Hugoniot relation. The space enclosed by the shock-tube is prescribed the properties of water while the space that is outside the shock-tube is kept as a "void", allowing water to flow into it as a result of high-pressure wave impinging on the target. This has the effect of instantaneously relieving the pressure in the water-chamber in a manner consistent with experimental observations. In the case of specimen rupture, the CL framework allows water to flow out of the breached portion.

4.2 Constitutive and damage models for composite laminates

A finite-deformation framework is adopted to account for large deformations in the composite. Linear orthotropic elastic constitutive behavior is assumed. Damage initiation and failure of each composite ply are captured with Hashin's damage model [9, 10]. This is a homogenized model so that individual fibers and fiber-matrix interfaces are not modeled explicitly. Rather, the model provides a phenomenological representation of the different damage modes in composite structures. This framework incorporates four damage mechanisms: (1) matrix damage in tension, (2) matrix damage in compression, (3) fiber damage in tension, and (4) fiber damage in compression. The material properties for unidirectional carbon-fiber/epoxy composite used in these calculations were obtained from Chan et al. [11] and Pinho et al. [12].

4.3 Cohesive finite element framework

The cohesive finite element method (CFEM) has been extensively used to study a wide variety of issues related to delamination and fracture. Here, cohesive elements are specified at the interfaces between individual laminas in the composite structure as well as the interfaces between the aluminum and composite sections in the hybrid plates. The cohesive elements allow damage initiation and development in the interlaminar regions to be captured. A bilinear traction-separation law is adopted to describe the behavior of the cohesive elements [13].

5 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The structural attributes, loading intensities and constituent properties determine the overall fracture behavior through the activation of different fracture mechanisms which include delamination, interlaminar crack growth, intralaminar cracking, core-face debonding and fragmentation. In response to the impulsive loads specified in Fig. 2, a stress wave propagates through the curved composite laminate. The stress wave propagation is initially perpendicular to incident wave and follows the curvature of the cylindrical structure. Fig. 5 shows high speed photographs of a monolithic composite cylinder of thickness 5 mm subjected to an underwater impulsive load corresponding to a projectile velocity of 50 m/s. The high-speed photographs capture the dynamic deformation and warping in the composite cylinder. Figure 6 shows the post-test photographs of loaded specimens. Visual inspection reveals that delamination and fiber and matrix rupture are the major failure mechanisms in the cylindrical monolithic composite structure. Delamination is observed through the thickness in the filament wound plies while fiber and matrix cracking is observed on the inner and outer surfaces of the composite. For a similar incident impulse, the monolithic cylindrical sections experience significantly greater warping, delamination and cracking as compared to sandwich structures. In sandwich structures, the presence of the PVC foam core provides resilience and flexural stiffness and enhances the blast resistance of the structure. Consequently, the delamination and interlaminar cracking. On the impulse side, the outer face experiences interlaminar cracking and fiber-matrix debonding and the inner face is relatively undamaged. Permanent core compression is not extensive and is restricted to the HP100 foam close to the loaded area.

Overall, the following damage modes are observed in both structures:

- delamination and interlaminar cracking
- intralaminar cracking, matrix cracking and fiber rupture
- structural deformation and warping
- core compression and partial recovery.

Figure 4 High speed photographs of a monolithic composite structure subjected to an impulsive load generated by a projectile velocity of $V_0=50$ m/s.

6 NUMERICAL RESULTS

Results from the numerical analysis of the response of cylindrical composite structures to localized blasts provides insight and a more in-depth understanding of the failure modes, damage initiation and growth, velocity transfer and energy dissipation. A novel cohesive finite element framework provides a means of evaluating the blast resistance of composite structures through an explicit simulation of deformation processes in the structure. The boundary conditions applied to the model represent those applied in the experiments. The conditions closely resemble a cylindrical structure anchored to a larger structure, which is common for submarines, underwater pipelines and missiles. As in experiments, a planar underwater impulsive wave is incident on the side of the cylinder simulating a "side-on" loading condition.

Figure 5 Stress wave propagation in a cylindrical monolithic composite structure at different times.

Figure 6 Damage initiation and growth in cylindrical composite structure under impulsive loading. Delamination initiates at $t=200 \mu s$, and buckling occurs at $t = 400 \mu s$. At $t = 600 \mu s$, kinking occurs at the inner surface and causes cracking followed by rupture and fragmentation.

Figure 5 shows the stress wave propagation in a monolithic cylindrical composite structure. Figure 6 shows a sequence of magnified images showing the damage initiation and growth. As the stress wave propagates through the composite structure, the bonds between successive laminates fail and

delamination occurs at $t=200 \mu\text{s}$. When the interlaminar crack jumps from one interface to another, it inevitably leads to matrix cracking and intralaminar crack growth. Due to the dynamic nature of this process, buckling initiates in the composite structure and causes cracking and failure in the laminates as observed at $t=600 \mu\text{s}$. As deformation progresses, the intralaminar cracks link together to create a shear band along which the entire laminate undergoes failure and rupture. Figure 7 shows a comparison of experimentally measured and computationally calculated displacement and velocity of the inner surface of an impulsively loaded monolithic composite cylinder. The simulation predicts a lower value of permanent displacement and velocity but the final value is within 5% of the experimentally measured value.

Figure 7 Comparison of experimentally measured and computationally calculated displacement and velocity of the inner face in a monolithic cylindrical composite subjected to an impulsive load corresponding to $V_0 = 50\text{m/s}$.

Figure 8 Numerically calculated displacement and velocity as functions of time for the inner and outer face of a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected to an impulsive load corresponding to $V_0 = 50\text{m/s}$.

Figure 9 Energy dissipation through dynamic deformation, fracture and friction of failed surfaces as a function of time for the monolithic cylinder.

Figure 10 Energy dissipated in a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected to underwater impulsive loading.

Figure 11 Comparison of total energy dissipation in monolithic and sandwich structures subjected to similar impulsive loads.

The time histories of energy dissipation in the monolithic structure are shown in Figure 9(a-c). Dynamic compression in the bulk composite is the primary dissipation mechanism in the earlier stages of deformation, as the matrix absorbs the input energy and accommodates the imposed deformation. Accordingly, delamination initiates soon after the onset of the impulsive load as the interlaminar interfaces fail due to shear stresses. The failed surfaces interact with each other causing friction. The frictional dissipation in the structure is initially lower than fracture work but as the fracture surfaces interact with each other, frictional dissipation surpasses both strain energy as well as fracture work. Figure 9(b) shows the energy dissipated due to the creation of new crack surfaces while Figure 9(c) shows energy dissipation due to friction between failed surfaces.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The response of filament-wound cylindrical composite structures is investigated numerically and experimentally. The materials of choice are glass-fiber reinforced polymer and structural PVC foam, commonly found in marine construction. Underwater impulsive loading experiments are conducted at a fixed stand-off distance with impulsive loads similar to those observed in an underwater blast.

Experiments show that monolithic and sandwich composite structures exhibit multiple competing failure modes include core compression, delamination, core-face debonding, translaminar cracking, matrix and fiber rupture. Maximum core compression was observed on the side nearest to the blast loading indicating that the outer face deformed significantly into the core before recovering. For similar total mass, the sandwich structure provided considerably superior blast mitigation as compared to the monolithic structure. Overall, filament wound cylindrical structures exhibited good resiliency under blast loading. While the monolithic structure showed signs of severe internal damage and warpage, the sandwich structure was relatively unwarped and recovered most of the original geometry.

Numerical simulations carried out in this analysis provide an insight into the deformation mechanisms and energy dissipation in the composite structures. Simulations show that interlaminar delamination is an important damage mechanism. Delamination contributes to only 20% of the overall fracture work and ~ 5% of total energy dissipation and it is the driving force for other failure modes in the composite. Delamination precipitates the formation of intralaminar and translaminar cracks which lead to catastrophic failure and rupture. Additionally, interlaminar cracks span across large sections of the composite structure while fiber and matrix cracking is restricted to small regions close to the loading area. Simulations reveal that friction between cracked surfaces is major source of energy expenditure and is comparable in magnitude to fracture work and strain energy. Cracking and friction at the core face interface is found to be negligible in all cases. This can be attributed to the presence of the low density foam core which does not provide a significant resistance to shear deformation.

Computations reveal that cylindrical sandwich structures outperform monolithic structures significantly. The sandwich core helps mitigate the effects of high pressures on the cylindrical structure. Figure 11 shows a comparison of energy dissipation in the form of fracture, friction and elastic strain. Results indicate that for a similar applied impulse, the sandwich structure dissipates almost twice as much energy as the monolithic structure. This is primarily because of the presence of a compressible foam core and a thinner outer face which contribute to higher elastic strain and fracture work respectively.

The numerical capability can be utilized to design and optimize curved fiber composite structures subjected to side loading in navy vessels. In such an approach, the newly developed numerical scheme can provide an accurate and physically realistic representation of experimental results. This numerical scheme can be used with a variety of materials and structural geometries.

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